

PROBLEMS OF PROVIDING AGRICULTURE WITH EXPERT PERSONNEL DURING THE SOVIET PERIOD (2ND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182613>

Abstract: the article describes the problems of providing agriculture with specialist personnel in Uzbekistan during the Soviet period in the second half of the 20th century. Statistical data on the organization of collective farms and savkhozes were also analyzed.

Key words: collective farm, state farm, technical school, mechanization staff, mechanization technical school, mechanizer

The 2nd session of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, adopted on December 24, 1958, the law "On strengthening the connection between school and marriage and on the further development of the system of public education in the USSR" had a profound effect on the provision of professional and technical education to agricultural personnel, vocational and technical education, and the further development of the state system. increased by 54%. All types of vocational educational institutions operating in the country have become urban and rural vocational and technical educational institutions (HTBY) with a duration of study of one to three years. This event made it possible to introduce complex theoretical subjects into the educational course and expand the professional knowledge of rural youth. In Uzbekistan, the first rural HTBYs were established in 1959, and in 1961-1965, their number reached 130. The volume of training of specialists in the agricultural technical schools of the republic increased year by year. For example, 4723 agricultural specialists were trained in 1956-1960. Since the Law on School was issued, educational institutions of agricultural mechanization trained 34,790 mechanists, including 2,760 tractor drivers and 2,285 mechanics-drivers for cotton picking machines in 1962 alone, and first of all, it was necessary to provide educational institutions with specially qualified pedagogic personnel, foremen and modern equipment. It should be noted that there were also negative situations in vocational schools, such as overwriting and expulsion from the percentage system, due to system defects. Working based on quantitative indicators, not quality indicators, became the basis for the activity of educational institutions. This situation is especially high in rural vocational and technical educational institutions, most of them were filled at the expense of schoolchildren with a low level of general preparation. Such urgent problems have not been sufficiently solved in many educational institutions. As a result, agricultural personnel who are not well prepared, who do not know the full practices of their field, who cannot quickly adapt to modern equipment due to their lack of understanding of the new techniques and technologies introduced in production, have turned out.

From the second half of the 1960s, several works were carried out in the republic to train specialists of various specialties and send them to farms, to improve the quality of personnel. In particular, in 1960-1970, 7358 specialists were trained at the Tashkent Agricultural Institute. In 1961, 1,870 out of 2,452 students at the institute were

representatives of the local nationality, and in 1969, 2,875 out of 3,157 were Uzbeks. As a result, the number of specialists with diplomas who received education in higher educational institutions and received agricultural education became more active in collective farms and state farms of the republic. After the decision "On the most necessary measures in the field of further development of agriculture" at the plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU on March 24, 1965, a regular procedure for the provision of personnel and retraining of agriculture was established in the country. As a continuation of this, in accordance with the decision "On further improvement of the system of training of collective farm and state farms' management personnel and agricultural specialists" adopted in January 1966, together with the retraining of agricultural production organizers and the reorganization of their training system, study periods were determined for each category of employees. Since then, the output of specialists with higher and secondary specialized agricultural education has increased significantly, the quality of their training has improved somewhat, and about one million managers and specialists of farms have undergone retraining. In 1966, there were 84 faculties of advanced training under agricultural higher educational institutions in the country, where more than 120,000 collective farm chairmen and state farm directors, agricultural specialists studied here every year. The purpose of these works was to provide collective farm-state production with leaders and specialists who have high political and special training, who are aware of innovation. However, although advanced training courses at agricultural higher educational institutions are beneficial in the retraining of personnel, the educational process in the courses was not fully satisfactory. In the courses of this content, repeated education was provided based on the programs of higher and secondary special educational institutions. It was difficult for those who did not have enough general and special knowledge to master it. In addition, the education of the courses was overloaded with ideological subjects, and the main subjects became secondary.

In February 1968, the Central Committee of the Central Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the UzSSR adopted a decision "On measures to further develop secondary special education in the Uzbek SSR". The important aspect of this decision is that in 1968-1972, it was emphasized the need to establish agricultural technical schools. Within two years, 10 new secondary special educational institutions were established in the republic, among them there were agricultural technical schools in Samarkand and Syrdarya regions, hydromelioration technical school in Khorezm region, Chimboy agricultural mechanization technical school under Chimboy state farm in Karakalpakstan ASSR, Khojayli agricultural mechanization technical school under Shumanoi state farm. In order to increase the level of training of personnel for agriculture, Syrdarya agricultural mechanization and Tashkent agricultural technical schools were designated as the base. As a result, during the years 1968-1970, the work of training technicians in twenty-two specialties for cotton growing was started in the republic, and in the collective farms and state farms of the republic, there were 8136 people with higher education, and 17608 people with secondary special education.

The decision of the leadership in August 1974 "On the work in the field of retraining and professional development of management personnel and specialists of agricultural organizations, collective farms and state farms" established a system of activities aimed at improving the retraining and professional development of agricultural personnel in the republic in accordance with the "Leninist" principles of selection, training and placement of

agricultural personnel. As a result, personnel training in higher and secondary special educational institutions was expanded. In 1965, 10,400 highly educated agricultural specialists worked in Uzbekistan, and by 1980, their number was 15,400. Nevertheless, in Uzbekistan in 1974, the level of education of collective farm chairmen, department managers, zootechnicians, veterinary workers, engineers and technicians, managers and foremen of livestock farms was below average. That is, according to the state of research on April 1, 1974, in the total number of managers and specialists of state farms, 30.4% have higher education, 30.8% have secondary specialized education, and 16.4% and 29.4% in collective farms. It was necessary to equip the lim with modern technical means and use them widely.

Between 1976 and 1985, the number of managers and specialists in collective farms and state farms increased from 58,400 to 80,300, including specialists with higher and secondary education, from 32,900 to 59,000. In the early 1980s, 13,900 highly educated specialists worked in auxiliary agricultural enterprises in collective farms and state farms. In total, at the beginning of these five years, 8,519 agronomists, 7,108 zoo-veterinarians, engineers-technicians and other employees worked. Some work has been done in the field of providing agriculture with human resources, the number of people receiving education in the fields of agriculture in higher educational institutions and technical institutes has been steadily increasing. As a result, the number of industrial and technical intellectuals in the villages increased significantly, and the number of highly educated employees in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan in 1985 reached 47,800 people, and the number of employees with secondary specialized education reached 83,500 people. It was during these years that 6 higher educational institutions, 44 technical schools and a number of other special educational institutions trained specialists for agriculture in the country. In particular, Tashkent Institute of National Economy trained economists for agricultural planning, Tashkent State University trained agrochemical specialists. It should be noted that although the quality of agricultural specialists has slightly improved, the center, in order to cover up its guilt, blames the lack of responsibility of personnel as the main reason for the stagnation of the country's agriculture. In fact, the union did not take into account the local conditions and gave too many uniform instructions to the collective farms and state farms, the leaders and experts in the village stifled the initiatives of all the workers and prevented them from managing the work properly. One of the reasons for the backwardness of agricultural work was the mistreatment of local experts, disregard for their knowledge and experience.

In July 1970, at the 11th Plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU and the 11th Plenum of the Central Committee of the CPSU, focusing on creating conditions for the further growth of agriculture, the task of increasing the number of mechanized personnel and increasing labor productivity was considered as a separate issue. The reason is that by these years, staff unemployment was high due to the complexity of the work of mechanized personnel, lack of provision of cultural and household services to the rural population, and the organization of labor. Many mechanics moved to other industries where the conditions were easier without upgrading their skills. L. I. Brezhnev said in his report, "Nowadays, in order to solve the problems, it is necessary to increase the staff of mechanics. The mechanic is a central figure in the village. Without them, it will be difficult to solve the tasks of increasing agricultural production," he said.

In 1970, according to the information of the Department of Agriculture of Uzbekistan, there was a high need for mechanized personnel in organizations, that is, in the 1960s and 1970s,

the average annual growth of tractor fleets and cotton ginning machines was 8%, while the growth of mechanized personnel was 5.5%. In 1966-1969, this growth was as follows: the growth of personnel in this field was 2.2%, while the growth of car and tractor fleets was 6%. In 1961, there were 103 tractor drivers per 100 working tractors, and by 1970, it was 90.5 in the regions of the republic. The total number of tractors in collective farms and state farms of the republic increased from 90,000 in 1965 to 160,000 in 1979, from 21,000 to 31,000 cotton pickers, from 29,000 to 50,000 trucks. During these years, cotton picking was 57% mechanized. Therefore, in 1970 alone, it is shown in the archive that the cars remained idle in the parks due to a lack of 42,000 mechanics.

In the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan, there was a big difference in the work of mechanized personnel compared to other regions of the country. The significant decrease in the number of mechanized personnel is due to the severity of the work process, the poisoning of the natural environment, the inconvenience of the equipment, and other reasons. Thick dust, air temperature reaching 40-43 degrees in summer made it difficult for tractor drivers to breathe. Because of this, they had a high incidence of chronic diseases. According to the investigations, most of the mechanics were forced to quit the tractor-making profession at the age of 40-45, despite the fact that they have few years left to the retirement age. Only 3% of workers were under 45 years old, 1% were over 50 years old. However, during these periods, chemical fertilization of the land was carried out at a high level according to the instructions of the Union. If in 1965, 2 mln. 548 tons of chemical fertilizers were supplied, and in 1979 this amount was 5 million. was more than a ton. However, old-age pensions were given to mechanics who worked in the field of cotton production, in the same way as workers and servants working in other agricultural fields. They were not given additional benefits for working in a harsh and harmful environment.

According to the medical examination data, 60-75% of every 700 mechanists have chronic diseases, and unfavorable factors in production caused chronic diseases of the respiratory organs, stomach and duodenum. The majority of those suffering from these diseases are tractor drivers. As a result, 85% of tractor drivers in the age of 45-50 became disabled due to the increase of such diseases. In these years, cases of death of patients were recorded, that is, from 1963 to 1968, in agriculture, it increased from 1.4% to 5.6%, i.e. 4 times, and in the national economy of the republic, this indicator increased from 1.24% to 2.47%, i.e. it increased by 2 times.

At that time, cotton picking machines with a tightly closed structure and a cabin with an air cleaning device had not yet been created. Although the cabin of the MTZ-50 cotton picker had an air purifier, it was not suitable for the strong evaporation of water during very hot summer days. The Tashkent tractor factory did not solve the task of creating tractors with comfortable cabins. The costs of labor and equipment safety protection for agricultural workers of the republic have grown very slowly. This indicator increased by 18.4% in 1963-1970, while the growth in the national economy was somewhat higher, at 51%. It can be seen that the amount allocated for agriculture was 10 times lower than for the national economy. At the same time, it should be noted that the rate of growth of the funds allocated by the state to the national economy for the safety of workers is also not satisfactory. However, at that time, one of the main tasks of the state was to pay attention to the improvement of their quality and social status, along with increasing the number of personnel. Despite these problems, efforts to increase the supply of mechanized personnel to collective farms and state farms in Uzbekistan have been expanded. In 1975 alone, there were

86 rural vocational and technical educational institutions training mechanized personnel for agriculture. As a result, during 1965-1977, the number of employees employed in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan was 28.7%, and the number of mechanized personnel increased by 68.1%. In 1973, the number of machinists reached 166,900. In 1981 - 1985, the total number of mechanists who graduated from technical vocational schools and other forms of production training was 657.2 thousand people. In these years, 149.6 people acquired a new profession and 381.7 thousand people improved their skills in collective farms of the republic. In 1985-1987, 226,600 mechanists were trained in vocational and technical educational institutions, as well as in collective farms, state farms and other agricultural enterprises. There were times when an average of 100,000 mechanist personnel were trained per year. As a result, some of these personnel could not find a job in their specialty, having acquired the profession of mechanization, and joined the ranks of workers performing various tasks. In this case, it should be noted that there are serious imbalances in the branch structure of the vocational and technical education system, and for a long time, the power of this system was focused mainly on agriculture, the mass personnel of collective farms and state farms, especially the problem of mechanization personnel, became of primary importance, as a result, training of personnel for other sectors was carried out in relatively small quantities. Another problem is that educational institutions that prepare mechanized personnel for the construction of agriculture and water management in Uzbekistan are actually provided with only 40% of equipment and machinery. For example, 38 tractors were on average in Belarus for one vocational and technical educational institution of the Union, and only 8 tractors in the republic. Organizations and enterprises mainly handed over used, obsolete equipment, machines and mechanisms to vocational and technical educational institutions in their homelands. These problems, in turn, did not allow the training of skilled mechanized personnel.

References:

1. Социологические исследования. 1989. - №1. - С, 14.
2. Эргашева Ю.А. Культура Узбекистана: тенденции и проблемы развития. (50-60-е годы). - Т.: «Фан», 1997. - С. 132.
3. Iymanova D. Personnel policy of the Soviet system in Uzbekistan and its consequences. - Т.: "New century generation" 2013. -B.133-134.
4. Iymanova D. Personnel policy of the Soviet system in Uzbekistan and its consequences. - Т.: "New century generation" 2013. -B.136-137.
5. Iymanova D. Personnel policy of the Soviet system in Uzbekistan and its consequences. - Т.: "New century generation" 2013. -B.136-137.
6. Suyunov S.H. Science and technology development and personnel training. - Т.: "Uzbekistan", 1987.- B. 11.
7. Iymanova D. Personnel policy of the Soviet system in Uzbekistan and its consequences. - Т.: "New century generation" 2013. -B.138.
8. New history of Uzbekistan. The second book. Uzbekistan during the Soviet colonial period. - Т.: "Shark", 2000. - B. 550.
9. Iymanova D. Personnel policy of the Soviet system in Uzbekistan and its consequences. - Т.: "New century generation" 2013. -B.140-141.

